

Hemingway's Hills like White Elephants and Hartmann's Concepts of Reaction Formation and Sublimations

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>This study aims to offer a comprehensive discussion of the representations of reaction formation and sublimations in Hemingway's Hills like White Elephants in the light of Hartmann's ideas about ego psychology. This library-based study follows the descriptive-analytical methodology to investigate Hemingway's Hills like White Elephants from an ego-psychological perspective, through the theoretical principles of Heinz Hartmann according to his definition of reaction formation and sublimations. This study can be important for those who are interested in psychological literature. It can be a guideline for understanding human Being is behavior. Therefore, this study will promote better understanding of the abovementioned short story of Hemingway and explain what the concepts of Reaction Formation and Sublimations mechanisms are, so that readers can apply them to solve problems in their real lives. It is very likely that the characters of the short story employ the mechanisms of reaction formation and sublimations in order to overcome their anxiety, in an attempt to reduce the sense of loss they will suffer. The novelty of the present study lies in discussing the behavior of the characters as defensive mechanisms to reduce their anxiety about core issues, which can be able to help us better understand human behavior, then it must surely be able to help us understanding the literary texts that relate to human behavior.</i></p>
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Introduction

Psychoanalysis can be defined as a set of methods and methods that are employed to treat psychological and emotional problems that people face during their lives, as these techniques together constitute the method of treating mental disorders (Thompson, 2002). According to Frosh (2012), psychoanalysis is considered one of the most important intellectual and practical projects and the most influential in our modern era. It was Sigmund Freud and others who laid the foundations for this science at the end of the nineteenth century, during the same period that other major social sciences such as psychology and sociology emerged. Freud's students, including Heinz Hartmann, had great merit in developing this science. The idea of psychoanalysis emerged very early, possibly even from the beginning, but with narrower and broader goals, and began to gain serious attention during the reign of Sigmund Freud, who formulated his own theory of psychoanalysis in Vienna in the 1890s. Psychoanalysis was subsequently evolved in different courses, primarily by students of Freud, such as Heinz Hartmann (Birnbach, 1961).

In research from Meadow and Lemert (2003), it has been reported that here is nothing better than the unconscious to begin with to understand the method of treatment that is used in psychoanalysis today, as Freud described this indicating that the nucleus of the unconscious contains impulses seeking to get rid of cathexes. The different and conflicting motives and pressures of act, exist side by side without any influence on each other, although they may combine to form an intermediate goal or a compromise. Moreover, the contents of the unconscious are stable, do not change with the passage of time and contain no indication of time, and are not affected by external reality. Drives are activated only by their relative strength without any influence by external reality.

At the time, the primary focus of psychoanalysis was on Id and instinctive motives, and then new problems, notions, formulas, and new needs emerged that needed to be interpreted, and it transcended this narrower field towards a general theory of psychological life. The most decisive and clear step in this direction was the emergence of modern ego psychology through Freud's works in the past fifteen years and the investigative paths that those works opened, then Anna Freud studies, and in another area, those of the English school. There is no longer any doubt that psychoanalysis can claim to be general psychology in the broadest sense of the word, and our concept of methods of work that can properly be considered psychoanalysis has become broader, deeper, and more distinct than before (Hartmann, 1958).

According to new research about the present state of psychoanalysis, the great discrepancy between the Freud's contributions and those of his successors has been recognized, especially with regard to its inferential

nature, and this fact is attributed to the difficulty that analysts face in distinguishing the method from theory and practice. Psychoanalysis cannot reach independence as a complete science unless it can differentiate between its approach to practices and theories, and use it in a way that suits it. Taking into account the writings of Freud, it can be concluded that there is an idea that belongs to literature, and that psychoanalysis itself, its analysts, and the patients are fictional products of this thought (Barone & Costa, 2017). Psychoanalytic critique often ignores the textuality and verbal aspects of texts in favor of the Freudian motifs that are presumably hidden in their depths (Ellmann, 1994).

Hartmann was a pioneering clinical analyst, educator, theorist, and one of the most important psychologists who based their theories on Freud's ideas and his findings and was credited with developing them. Hartmann was considered one of the founders of psychoanalysis of that period, and was interested in psychosocial thinking, contributions of general biology, neuroscience, medicine as well as psychology and developmental theory. Hartmann considered psychoanalysis a center of general psychology. He is best known for his works and contributions to the psychology of ego and adaptation, the development of conflict theory and drive, and the conflict-free sphere of the ego (Encyclopedia, 2020).

Hemingway's iceberg hypothesis highlights the typical implications of art. He makes utilize of action to supply an elucidation of the nature of human existence. It can be convincingly demonstrated that "while speaking to human life through anecdotal shapes, he has reliably set human against the foundation of his world and universe to look at the human circumstances from different points of view" (Halliday, 1956).

Critique of Hemingway's short story has grown exponentially. More importantly, despite the fact that the popularity of many of his short stories is increasing continuously, they can be considered a great contribution of Hemingway to literature. Additionally, the animosity inspired by Hemingway's public figures, which had made many academics criticize his work, gradually dissipated. In fact, the change in the author's stature has been so dramatic, although it has occurred so progressively over the past two decades that few have backed away from it and commented on it (Benson, 2013).

While much of the criticism on *Hills Like White Elephants* has focused on symbolism (Renner, 1995) and antifeminism (Rankin, 2005), there is no comprehensive discussion of the representations of the sublimation and reaction formation in the light of Hartmann's ideas about ego psychology. This study offers such a comprehensive discussion. In order to examine Hemingway's *Hills like White Elephants* in the light of the concepts of the sublimation and reaction formation, the present study focuses on the representations of these psychological mechanisms in aforementioned short story in terms of Hartmann's theories.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This library-based study follows the descriptive-analytical methodology to investigate Hemingway's *Hills like White Elephants* from an ego-psychological perspective, through the theoretical principles of Heinz Hartmann according to his definition of the sublimation and reaction formation. It is the contention of this study that the sublimation and reaction formation mechanisms are developed by the people represented by Hemingway's characters in *Hills Like White Elephants*. The general theoretical framework for the discussion is Heinz Hartmann's analytical studies of the human psyche outlining his theories of the ego psychology. However, we are going to decontextualize the selected short story of Ernest Hemingway and discuss it within the network of signification they create in the text. It is better to explore the personality structure of characters. Therefore, the way the characters develop the sublimation and reaction formation mechanisms will be investigated. The steps to conduct this research include determining data and data sources, the technique of data collection, and technique of data analysis. There are two data sources needed to perform this research, namely: primary data sources and secondary data sources. The primary data sources are the abovementioned short story of Ernest Hemingway. The secondary data sources are other sources related to the study, such as websites, dictionaries, and some books that support the analysis. The technique of data analysis is note-taking as the method of collecting data in this research. Heinz Hartmann's analytical studies of the human psyche and the sublimation and reaction formation mechanisms help us better understand the social problems cause personal problems for people represented by Hemingway's character and the aspects of his work that challenge us to figure out where we stand on such world and why.

The concept of Sublimation

While reading *The Harz Journey* by Heinrich Heine, Freud came to what he called "sublimation". The story revolves around Johann Friedrich Dieffenbach who cut dog tails when he was a child and later became a surgeon. It has been suggested that sublimation can be a conflict between the need for satisfaction and the need for security without disturbing consciousness. Sublimation is an action that an individual performs several times throughout his life turns into an activity that benefits humanity (Jay Geller, 2009).

Following Freud, three types of energy have been distinguished: libidinal, aggressive, and neutral. The neutral energy belongs to the ego from the very beginning, it is formed and used by the ego mainly against the pressure of the libidinal and aggressive energies. The ego increases its reserve of neutral energy by "neutralizing" the other two types, which enhances the ego's ability to adapt and thus helps it to carry out its

creative activities through behaviors that sublimation is one of them. This explains the energy process that occurs during sublimation (Gay, 1992).

The most frequent description suggests that the "sublimation" is a deviation from sexual motivations from instinctive goals to goals or values that are acceptable the in cultural and social level. Objects may also be subject to change. Based on this definition, sublimation is, in fact, a special kind of displacement, that is, this condition only includes displacement which cause the replacement of valuable goals and values. This approach is distinguished by clearly stating that sexual orientation may be the root of the achievements of the human sciences and religion (Hartmann, 1955). Sublimation is the only adaptive defense mechanism that enables the expression of libidinal and aggressive impulses in an alternative form in which repression cannot play a role (Comunian & Gielen, 1994). In research from Heimann and Tonnesmann (2005), It is reported that Hartmann conducted a historical and critical survey about the development of the concept of sublimation, rescuing it from the theory that considers it the ability of the "few" only, leaving room in his own theory of sublimation for temporary increases or decreases in sublimation activities, presenting sublimation as a continuous process and not an occasional event.

According to Forsch (1971), Hartmann considers in his critical writings that the ability to sublimate is limited. In his own work, sublimation is seen as a process rather than an act. Hartmann urged a better understanding of the factors that promote or delay sublimation in children. He agreed with Anna Freud and others that sublimation could act as a defense but he showed that he had very important non-defensive functions as well. He warned against the misleading equation of sublimation with normality. He explained that changes in the degree of neutralization do not always change instinctive goals. The defenses themselves, including the reaction formation, also depend on neutral energy (Richards & Willick, 2019).

Richards & Willick (2019) believe that Hartmann confused our understanding of his proposals on neutralization by writing about neutrality in a way that clearly isolated drives from mental content. Hartmann's concept of neutralization includes the maturation of the ego and the development of its functions and structures, but there are some weaknesses in the concept of sublimation by neutralization, and the most important of these weaknesses is that it ignores some fundamental aspects that cannot be derived from considerations of energy alone (Feigenbaum et al., 2011).

The concept of Reaction Formation

Reaction formations are irrational adjustments to anxiety. They expend energy for deceptive and hypocritical purposes. They distort reality and they make the personality rigid and inflexible. This belief is used by people who feel hated and persecuted in order to attack their hypothetical enemy, as they are satisfied with the hostile motivations when they use the pretext to defend themselves against these imaginary enemies. For example, if a person feels hate toward another person, and anxiety arises from that feeling, the ego can assist the flow of love in order to hide feelings of hate and hostility. We cannot say that hate is replaced by love, because this is not correct, as aggressive feelings still exist under the affectionate outer cover. It would be better to say that love is a mask that conceals hatred under it. This mechanism by which an instinct is hidden from consciousness as opposed to it is called the reaction formation (Hall, 1999). Reaction formation is an extreme and often dangerous defense mechanism. "Reaction formation occurs when someone adopts feelings, attitudes, or behaviors that are the opposite of desires and impulses he or she may unconsciously hold but find unacceptable" (Kittleson et al., 2005, p.41). "Reaction formation is a defense mechanism in which an affect is disguised as its opposite" (Busch, 2011, p.97).

Reaction formation is a transitional defense mechanism between action level defense and mature altruistic defense. It has been suggested that reaction formation a reaction is often used to hide the expression of unacceptable anger, sexual activity, or dependency. Examples include behaving kindly by someone who feels hateful, fearful, or angry, or to show interest in someone that one really wants to get attention from (Minges et al., 2017). The original idea of the reaction formation is relevant to the act of sexual and aggressive impulses (Baumeister et al., 1998).

Concerned that sublimation provides an exit from instinctive impulses in another pattern has made them a basis for distinguishing them from the reaction formation. Reaction formation arises in ego defensive system. It will also be used later in its counter-cathetic aspects, but we should take into account that, for example, the traits of the interactive character, in the context of development, will also be invested with other non-defensive functions within the ego environment, far from the fact that Freud has observed before, namely it may also be based on instinctive tendencies opposed to those built to get rid of them. Glover integrates the reaction formation under displacement, and defines it as a displacement in the opposite direction (Hartmann, 1955). It can be said that the formation of the reactive character, arising from defense against drives, may gradually assume a host of other functions within the framework of the ego (McCarthy, 2000).

Emphasis has been placed on the "secondary autonomy" of defenses and their ability to transform into objects of high cultural value. For example, reaction formation is a defense that is employed to play a role in keeping one consciously unaware of the persistent and socially unacceptable pleasure involved in bathroom activities, and the child's pleasure resulting from his bowel movements becomes a conscious attitude of disgust.

However, the reaction formation arising from conflict may ultimately serve a highly adaptive function in the public character as true pleasure in good hygiene and arrangement, and thus transform into a process occurring outside of conflict (Rosen-Carole, 2013).

Hemingway's *Hills Like White Elephants*, an overview

The story revolves around an American man and girl waiting for a train at a Spanish railway station to go to Madrid. They drink beer in addition to other drinks, then drink a lot of beer, and they sit in the hot shade and discuss what the American guy has to say about a simple operation that will be performed for the girl. The tension between the two is almost as intense as the heat of the Spanish sun. While the guy has been urging the girl to have the operation, he repeatedly said that he really doesn't want her to have it if she doesn't really want it, but he insists she should. The girl tries to be brave and indifferent but is clearly afraid of committing herself to the operation. The girl notes that the hills behind the train station are like white elephants, hoping that the form of speech will please the man, but he is upset at their ruse. He insists on talking more about the process and the fact that it is natural and not really practical at all. The express train arrives and the two are getting ready to ride. The girl tells the man that she is fine. She lies, acquiesces to what he wants, and hopes to calm him. Nevertheless, tension remains as they prepare to leave for Madrid. The girl is hurt by the man's hypocrisy and lies, and is terribly afraid of the operation that she will undergo in Madrid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Concept of Sublimation in Hemingway's *Hills like White Elephants*

Each reader should come to his/her own conclusion based on the dialogue that is taking place in the story, and this leads to different interpretations since there is not much information about the characters and other aspects. One of the points of contention is whether or not the girl decides to have an abortion, although the details in the story indicate that the woman decided to keep the child. The author did not provide us with any information that would benefit us in interacting with the characters of the story. He did not mention that the girl, for example, spoke with anxiety, anger, confusion, or indifference, nor did he tell us that the man is in a better position.

When the girl looks outside, she clearly sees the hills and says that they look like white elephants, and the man replies, saying that he had never seen a white elephant before. Here, tension rises between the man and the girl until the girl changes the topic of the conversation, apologizing to him saying that he is right and that the hills do not really look like white elephants and that she only meant that their skin was colored through the trees. It is controversial here to note that the hills do not look like white elephants and have no skins of course, but the girl distanced herself in her fantasy world from the rational world of the man. She knows that the things she desires will never come true, so she is employing her unwanted feelings for something constructive and positive which is to unleash her artistic imagination and her perception of the hills as white elephants. It is this constructive use of unwanted emotions that we call sublimation. This constructive use is best illustrated when the girl looks across the river at the fields and fertile land that contrasts with the sterility of the barren hills that the girl portrayed as white elephants, knowing that she must undergo an abortion that may lead to her sterility due to the presence of a man who does not deserve her, although The story does not indicate what you will do in the end.

Sublimation is an action or group of actions that an individual carries out during his/ her life and through which unwanted feelings and motives are transformed into a constructive and useful activity and acceptable goals or values at the cultural and social level. We notice during the course of the story and during the dialogues that took place between the man and the girl that the girl uses the sublimation mechanism again in a constructive way to refuse being completely dependent on the man and become a self-confident person aware of what is around her and what can be expected from her, where at the end of the dialogue she takes control of herself and the situation and she asks the man to be silent, repeating the word "please" seven times, indicating that she can no longer bear his hypocrisy and his constant repetition of the same topic. The girl "aborted" those unwanted feelings that she was suffering from and replaced them with goals or values that are culturally and socially acceptable, represented in independence, self-confidence and perhaps "refusing" to comply with the requests of the man who was insisting that she perform the abortion.

The concept of Reaction Formation

The dialogue that takes place between the man and the girl indicates that dealing with any issue, no matter how small, raises the level of tension and anger between them, yet each of them continues to try to maintain the natural appearance, entertainment and freedom to convince the other that everything is fine and that things are not as they seem. It has been previously mentioned that reaction formation is the adoption of feelings, attitudes, and behaviors that contradict the unacceptable desires and motives of the unconscious. The man seems to be more using the reaction formation mechanism, as he tries to pretend to enjoy the time and tells the girl that her perception of the hills as white elephants is a clever perception and that beer is wonderful and cool, but the girl seems skeptical about this pretense of happiness, and hints that there are serious problems in their relationship that they refuse to discuss openly.

The man insists that the abortion operation is simple and logical, which conflicts with the feelings of the girl who wants to preserve her pregnancy, as the girl mocks his words and feels doubt about his persistence, while he sees the abortion as an opportunity to return to their previous, calm and enjoyable relationship. The man does not spare any effort in persuading the girl to undergo the operation, repeatedly saying that it is a simple operation in an attempt to make her feel that this is what she wants. Although this dialogue reveals the different ways in which both the man and the girl view the pregnancy of the girl, but the man's insistence on improving the image of abortion and its consequences, which are represented in a return to the previous and enjoyable relationship, may also express his feelings of guilt and his denial of the rejected and unwanted feelings represented in his desire that the girl has an abortion. Perhaps his formulation of his request in a romantic way and trying to convince the girl that this is what she wants can be seen as the process of reaction formation by which he represses his unwanted and rejected emotions or desires and expresses them outwardly in a contrasting or opposite form.

CONCLUSION

This research discussed the behavior of the characters of Hemingway's *Hills Like White Elephants* as defensive mechanisms through the theoretical principles of Heinz Hartmann according to his definition of reaction formation and sublimations. It is very likely that the girl employs the sublimation to use her unwanted feelings for something constructive and positive which is to unleash her artistic imagination and her perception of the hills as white elephants, because she knows that the things she desires will never come true. As the story shows, the man's insistence on improving the image of abortion and its consequences, which are represented in a return to the previous and enjoyable relationship, may also express his feelings of guilt and his denial of the rejected and unwanted feelings represented in his desire that the girl has an abortion.

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